

MODERN METHODS OF RISK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IMPROVEMENT IN CUSTOMS AUTHORITIES

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Abstract: This thesis examines the risk management system practices in the customs authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan and proposes recommendations for its development based on modern methodologies.

Keywords: Risk, risk management, foreign economic activity participants, risk management system, customs, risk identification, customs control.

Today, the risk management system is recognized as a tool for optimizing customs control, preventing illegal activities, and accelerating trade flows. The customs system of Uzbekistan is also carrying out significant reforms in this direction.

The expansion of the scope of risk management system usage serves to optimize existing requirements for trade facilitation, develop cooperation with the trade community, and creates necessary conditions to ensure balance between effective control and trade facilitation. In this regard, new approaches to optimizing the risk management system, the experience of risk management systems in foreign countries, and opportunities for their utilization have been studied.

The essence and importance of risk management in customs authorities, modern methods of risk management, specific features of risk identification, mathematical models of risk management processes, and algorithms for classifying and evaluating customs risks based on multidimensional analysis of customs information have been researched by a number of scholars in our country, including A. Saidov, M.M. Xamrayev, A.O. Nazarov, X.B. Ro'zimetov, Sh.Sh. Shoha'zamiy, L.T. Pulatova, D.N. Sharipova, and appear in their scientific research and literature^{1,1}

¹ Saidov A.A. Methods of creating an automated management system of the State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. // Technical sciences doctoral dissertation abstract. -- T.: 2015. -- 43 p.; Xamrayev M., Ruzmetov X., Nazarov A. Risk Management System. // Textbook. -- T.: 2020. -- 260 p.; Shoha'zamiy Sh.Sh. Financial Market and Securities. // Textbook. --T.: 2007. --- 281 p.; Pulatova L.T., Saidov A.A. Problematic issues of implementing risk management systems in phytosanitary and veterinary control at

In particular, M.M. Xamrayev, A.O. Nazarov, and X.B. Ro'zimetov in their textbook "Risk Management System" noted that the application of the "Risk Management" system aimed at selecting forms and methods of customs control implementation, creating favorable conditions for honest foreign economic activity participants with low risk levels, drastically reducing time and costs for customs formalities, and preventing corruption has become an integral part of customs control[4].

Furthermore, Professor Joshua Angrist, in economic analysis and statistical methods, particularly methodologies for determining causality, emphasizes the necessity of quality data and reliable analytical methods in making effective and informed decisions[5]. This is also important in risk management and policy decision-making. Thomas Cantens, in his research within the World Customs Organization (WCO) framework, defines risk as unknown or uncontrolled threats in the customs control process. He states that more effective results can be achieved through the use of big data and artificial intelligence technologies in risk management[6]. His research is dedicated to predicting customs risks and reducing them through profiling.

By Presidential Decree PF-5414 of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 12, 2018, "On measures to fundamentally improve the activities of the state customs service bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan"[7], the Customs Committee was tasked with developing and implementing an automated risk management system that envisages selective customs control of goods.

For the purpose of further improving customs administration, simplifying customs procedures, increasing the efficiency of customs authorities' activities, ensuring compliance with customs legislation by foreign economic activity participants, encouraging honest entrepreneurs, and improving the investment environment in the country, Presidential Decree PF-5582 of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 24, 2018, "On additional measures to improve customs administration and increase the efficiency of the state customs service bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan"[3] was adopted, introducing "yellow" and "red" channels in the automated risk management system from December 1, 2018, and "green" and "blue" channels from March 1, 2019.

The risk management system was gradually implemented at border customs posts, including:

checkpoints across the customs border of the Republic of Uzbekistan; Sharipova D.N. Risk management in the personnel management system of customs authorities. -- 2016. [↩](#)

- ✚ 2020: automobile border customs posts
- ✚ 2021: railway and aviation border customs posts

The risk management system for customs control of international courier shipments was piloted from April 21, 2025.

Figure 1. Stages of risk management system implementation

By Presidential Decree PF-57 of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 25, 2025, "On measures to increase the efficiency of state customs service bodies"[8], the goal was set to:

- ✚ Increase the efficiency of the risk management system by 2 times by 2030 using artificial intelligence elements
- ✚ Double the share of human-factor-free customs declaration processing by 2026

Based on this, a new "Classification" module of the system will be created by increasing the weight of information about foreign economic activity participants based on data obtained from other ministries and departments, and customs cargo declarations with low risk levels, including transit declarations, will be processed fully automatically without human involvement.

Analyses show that certain problems existing in the system, particularly insufficient integration of databases and incomplete implementation of information technologies, affect the efficiency of risk identification. At the same time, it has been determined that the risk management system can be optimized through widespread introduction of digital technologies in customs activities, use of artificial intelligence and data analysis tools, and strengthening international cooperation. This, in turn, serves to simplify customs processes, prevent illegal activities, and increase foreign economic activity.

The implementation of the risk management system is of great importance in improving the investment environment in the country and encouraging honest entrepreneurs. Simplification of customs procedures improves the activities of foreign economic activity participants and increases compliance

with customs legislation. This, in turn, ensures sustainable development of the country's economy. Therefore, customs authorities need to focus on further improving the risk management system. There is a need to develop the risk management system in customs authorities by studying the experience of foreign countries. Based on the above, the following recommendations are made:

- ✚ To improve the system of expedited customs control of individuals entering the republic by analyzing them based on the "Risk Management" information system, integrate the State Security Service Border Guards information system with the Customs Committee information system for online exchange of biometric data and photographs of citizens crossing the state border;

- ✚ Implement a system for advance submission of information about individuals moving through border customs posts;

- ✚ Integrate risk management systems of phytosanitary and veterinary control bodies with customs authorities' information systems;

- ✚ Develop a risk module within the risk management system that ensures control of goods' TNVED codes from border entry until final regime registration;

- ✚ Implement artificial intelligence elements that automatically update themselves based on existing and incoming data in the risk management system.

In conclusion, as the foreign trade volume of the Republic of Uzbekistan continues to grow annually, the risk management system is the optimal method for expediting the movement of goods and transport vehicles through customs borders. Optimizing the risk management system is not only part of internal reforms for customs authorities but also an important tool for adapting to global trends and ensuring economic security.

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